

Structural-semantic features of commercial terminologic

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Abstract: This article examines the structural-semantic features and etymological features of the terminology "Financial and commercial activity" in the Uzbek language. The excessive number of differences between Uzbek terminology and other languages is explained by the existence of temporary ethno-cultural spaces in it, one of their main features is the possibility of elimination in certain extralinguistic conditions.

Key words: thematic group of vocabulary, interrelated vocabulary, borrowing, lexical spaces, flow of borrowings, extralinguistic factors.

There is no doubt that the modern Uzbek language, which serves the field of commercial and financial activities, is full of shortcomings. The components of the terminological group "Finance and commercial activity" also include common omissions (for example: dealer, broker, deposit, sale, distributor, share, grant, investment, leasing, price). A group of highly specialized terms used (for example: acceptance, letter of advice, attachment, decouper, debor, delivery, barrier, call credit) are included among these problems. At this point, the question arises, is this situation natural or is it an artificial "contamination" of the original terminology with foreign elements?

If we consider this phenomenon to be regular, what extralinguistic and linguistic processes became the objective conditions for the abundance of Russian-speaking words in the terminology of the language under consideration? If we consider the interrelated groups of Uzbek and Russian dictionaries from the point of view of lacunarity, we can find an answer to this question.

In particular, the terms "lacuna" and "lexical lacuna" are interpreted by different departments of linguistics and cultural studies using different conceptual units, as shown by the analysis of theoretical literature. In linguistics and psycholinguistics, "lacunae" are understood as the main elements of the national identity of the linguistic

and cultural community, which make it difficult for receivers of other cultures to understand some parts of the texts. The term "lacuna" is what linguist S. Stepanov called them "gaps", "white spots on the semantic map of the language". There are other terms for the concept of "Lacuna" (called "gap" in English-language literature): "accidental notes in speech patterns", ethnoeidemes, linguocultures, ethnolinguocultures. For example, according to the point of view presented in the monograph G.A. Antipova and others "The text as a cultural phenomenon", spaces are linguistic (lexical, grammatical, stylistic) and cultural (ethnographic, psychological, behavioral, kinesthetic and others) can be. Moreover, gaps can be not only intercultural or interlinguistic (emerging in the process of intercultural communication), but also intercultural (intralinguistic).

For the purpose of this research paper, as a working definition, it seems that we should choose the interlinguistic interpretation of the phenomenon, that is, the interpretation used in translation theory. A lacuna is the absence of a unit present in one language but present in another. The authors say that "the main feature of gaps is that they appear in the process of communication, in the conditions of communication between two cultures." In the work "Language and Translation" by the translator Barkhudarov, we find the following definition: "Gaps are vocabulary units of one of the languages, which for some reason do not correspond lexically. are the composition of another language". The additional linguistic "state of contact between two cultures" clearly shows that the linguistic phenomenon of vocabulary acquisition is related to the existence of ethnographic (cultural, intercultural) spaces. Ethnographic spaces sometimes exist in one culture in another Thus, in the Uzbek language, along with the word "lawyer" there are several other words to define the types of legal profession.

In linguistics, the word does not have a corresponding one-word equivalent: legal representative (has the right to speak in courts), lawyer (prepares cases for a lawyer), defender (advises clients), consultant (consultant on various legal issues), lawyer (highly qualified lawyer). In other cases, there is a wide gap in the language, because it is often not necessary to distinguish between things in a certain culture that are permanently distinguished by other cultures. However, ethnographic gaps, in our view, are permanent and temporary. can be Permanent ethnographic spaces are almost never filled with loans, they exist statically as an integral part of this or that linguistic picture of the world, giving it a certain identity. Thus, examples of permanent lacunae

in the Uzbek language are dealer, broker, deposit, sale, distributor, share, grant, investment, lease." These words entered the Uzbek language for commercial use from foreign languages. Temporary ethnographic spaces are a dynamic phenomenon associated only with certain stages of language development. Temporary gaps can be filled (increased) with loans at any time. Such spaces have the following characteristics (determined based on a comparison of Uzbek and Russian language materials):

1) The denotative basis of the gap is related to a certain field of economy, technology, politics, culture;

2) One of the compared language cultures does not have experience in this field of activity compared to the other, but the vector of development is aimed at overcoming it;

3) One of the compared language cultures perceives the gap as an obstacle in communicative activity;

4) The temporal gap can be eliminated under the influence of extralinguistic factors.

Note that the process of eliminating lacunae attracts the attention of researchers and is defined as a compensation for temporally non-equivalent terms in particular. The analysis of the literature shows that elimination of deficiencies in texts aimed at a foreign cultural recipient can be done in two ways: filling (translation using analog) and compensation. The most common way to compensate for deficiencies in financial and commercial activities is transcription (transfer at the phoneme level) and transliteration (transfer at the grapheme level). In turn, it became a translation that was mastered and frequently used at the grapheme and phoneme level.

A brief analysis of the features of Uzbek terminology in "Finance and Commercial Activity" allows us to form its main linguistic features: originality, capacity and description of semantics, compactness. The above two features (semantic capacity and structural compactness) make Uzbek terminology attractive as a source of enrichment, particularly for the Uzbek language.

Thus, the pragmatic approach, the principle of saving language efforts and the situation of inter-ethnic communication help the natural process of filling the temporary ethno-cultural gaps in the Uzbek language with words from other languages.

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